

RURITAGE

Heritage for Rural Regeneration

DSS light version

Rationale – Documentation – Outlook

D5.1

Due date of deliverable: 31-05-2019

Actual submission date: 30-06-2019

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Call: H2020-SC5-2016-2017

Number: 776465

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776465

Background Information

Table 1: technical Information

Project Full title		Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
Project Acronym		RURITAGE	
Grant Agreement No.		776465	
Coordinator		University of Bologna (UNIBO)	
Project start date and duration		June 2018 – May 2022 (48months)	
Project website		www.ruritage.eu	
Deliverable Nr.	5.1	31/05/2019	May 2019 (month 12)
		30/06/2019	June 2019 (month 13)
Work Package No		5	
Work Package Title		RURITAGE Resources Ecosystem	
Responsible		ALM	
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Reviewer(s) (if applicable)		[names] [org acronyms]	
Status:		Final (F)	●
		Draft (D)	
		Revised draft (RV)	
Dissemination level:		Public (PU)	●
		Confidential, only for members of the consortium (CO)	

Table 2: List of abbreviations

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
DSS	Decision Support System
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage

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Summary

In this deliverable we introduce the RURITAGE DSS. This system is aimed at helping replicators to find and compose effective strategies for the promotion of their heritage based on information collected from Role Models during the first year of the RURITAGE project.

We start with an explanation of the concept and objectives of the DSS and show how it relates to the work done in Work Package 1, in particular the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1) and the RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learnt (D1.2).

Secondly, we document the functionalities of a light version of the DSS that has been realized during the first year of the project. The light version of the DSS is based on the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1) only. This considerably limits its current functionality, as it does not use any information from the Lessons Learnt (D1.2) yet. Nevertheless, it is a functioning light version that is available online for use by both replicators (to assess the usefulness of the available RM data) and Role Models (to verify the information they provided at an earlier stage in the project).

Finally, we provide an outlook for future work on the DSS and a roadmap for its development during the remainder of the project. Future work will include the inclusion of lessons Learnt, further development of different techniques to bridge R profiles with RM data, and the adoption of multi-agent technology to incorporate the different exploration techniques into a coherent software framework.

1. Introduction to the DSS

The RURITAGE Decision Support System (DSS), according to the RURITAGE DoA, is “a system for supporting the discovery and composition of possible heritage-led regeneration scenarios”, which “considers previous initiatives and provides suggestions for combining good practices and Lessons Learnt from various RMs, allowing the choice of comprehensive programmes to be implemented at replicating sites”.

In this deliverable we explain the concept and objectives of the DSS, document the functionalities of the first (light) version which has been developed during the second half year of the project, and provide a roadmap for the further development of the DSS during the remaining three years of the project.

1.1 Concept and objectives

The RURITAGE DSS is meant to be used by Replicators (R): Rural territories in the EU and beyond that want to develop their heritage-led rural regeneration strategies. Based on a profile of a Replicator (i.e., information about its current baseline and desired state), it uses the data collected from Role Models (RM) to provide to the Replicator useful practices and Lessons Learnt in order to help the Replicator reaching its desired state.

The conceptual understanding of the DSS is straightforward (see Figure 1). It is organised as an interactive dashboard: Replicators are allowed to enter information about themselves (their current state and initial capital, the objectives they would like to achieve, the challenges they have in their territories, etc.). The DSS immediately searches through the available data collected from Role Models in the RURITAGE project (Best Practices, Lessons Learnt, etc.), analyses and combines the results, and provides a consistent advice to the user.

Figure 1: The DSS concept

Although the concept of the DSS is simple, it allows for all kinds of extensions in many different directions:

- On the **Replicator Profile** side, the information provided by Replicators about their current and desired state can range from very simple (e.g., selection of a particular Systemic Innovation Area (SIA) or provision of a few textual keywords) to fairly complex (e.g., provision of detailed quantitative information or upload of strategic roadmap documents). We also currently envision a multi-stage decision making model in which each stage requires more information from the replicator. For example, the user could start with navigating the content, in order to continue with finding an appropriate set of “twin” Role Models, after which she concludes with establishing a replicable set of Lessons Learnt.
- On the **Best Practices / Lessons Learnt** side, the database can be continuously extended with new information from Role Models *beyond* the best practices and lessons learnt stemming from D1.1 and D1.2, including for example references and links to other tools (within or even outside the RURITAGE Replicator Toolbox).
- With respect to the **Search and Reasoning Engine**, simple techniques like keyword search may be applied, but also more complex techniques like semantic search engines (which include an understanding of the intent of users and the contextual meaning of terms they use) or techniques to recombine information particles into a coherent advice (for example, create a replicable set of Lessons Learnt as mentioned above, perhaps even with a prioritization).
- The **Presentation of the Results** to the user can also range from simple textual or tabular representations to visual maps of solution combinations with diagrams, charts and timelines.
- We can apply **Learning Techniques** into the DSS based on the user interaction with the system: by recording the interaction of users with the system, the system may learn which information is appreciated in which situation. Next to implicit techniques (e.g., capturing the “mouse movements / clicks” of the user), also explicit feedback may be requested from users (e.g., asking the user to provide “likes” of the results the DSS shows).
- It is possible to adopt **Direct Manipulation** techniques into the DSS, by immediately showing the effects of the user interaction (e.g., a change of keywords entered into the system or the deselection of a certain option) in the presented results. This way, the system allows users to “play” with the results.

The main objective of the RURITAGE DSS is:

to enable Replicators to take informed decisions about which lessons learnt from the Role Models they should adopt when implementing their own heritage-led regeneration plans.

However, this is not only the main objective, but also the *minimal* objective. An important second objective is:

to explore the possibilities for extension of the RURITAGE DSS in various directions, in order to provide novel ways of support for the Replicators based on the collected information from Role Models and other types of data available in the RURITAGE ecosystem.

In Section 3, we will present a roadmap for the further development of the DSS which takes both objectives into account. The main objective is key during the first phase of the project (M1-M18), while the second objective will be at the core of the activities in the second phase (M19-M48).

1.2 System architecture

The RURITAGE DSS will be provided as an online tool, accessible via the internet. As the DSS is a data-rich tool with the intention to present a large amount of information to the end user in a single view, the tool is meant for use on laptops or desktops rather than for tablets or smartphones.

The back-end of the system will consist of a database (MongoDB) providing an Application Programming Interface

(API) to a Processing Engine, which takes care of the execution of the search and reasoning techniques. The Processing Engine is set up as a pool of Software Agents (autonomously running software entities), each representing and embodying a specific search and reasoning technique. The various reasoning techniques will be primarily based upon current open source state-of-the-art software components. An incremental approach is adopted for their implementation. The Processing Engine in turn provides a so-called REST API to a Javascript based front-end which runs in the browser of the user.

Important for the relevance of the RURITAGE DSS is the quality of the data present in the database. At this moment, the data consists of all information collected in the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1), which is a large MS Excel sheet compiled and maintained by Partner 3 (TECNALIA). The RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learnt (D1.2), also an MS Excel sheet compiled and maintained by TECNALIA, will be added to this soon. All information in the MS Excel sheets is semi-automatically converted into the JSON format by Partner 10 (POLITO) for inclusion in the database. The database is not only used by the DSS, but also by the RURITAGE Atlas (D1.3).

1.3 Deliverables and milestones

For the development of the DSS, two deliverables have been defined in the project. D5.1 (this deliverable) consists of a light version of the DSS based on the Role Model information available at M12. This version will first be tested by the RURITAGE Replicators.

Throughout M13 to M48, the DSS will be extended with new data and enhanced with new functionalities, and will eventually be integrated in the RURITAGE Replication Toolbox (D5.4). The extended version of the DSS will be tested by RURITAGE replicators as well as additional selected Replicators.

Hence, effectively, we have two milestones defined for the DSS: M12 and M48. Since the period between these two milestones is substantial, we provide a roadmap for the further development of the DSS (with additional milestones) in Section 0 of this document. The tests carried out by the Replicators are expected to take place at least after each of the additional milestones.

2. Overview of the DSS light version

The DSS light version takes into account the information available from the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1) and provides an interface to filter the available information based on simple selection criteria. It is available online for use by both replicators (to assess the usefulness of the available RM data) and Role Models (to verify the information they provided at an earlier stage in the project).

The RURITAGE DSS can be opened in any modern web browser like Chrome or Firefox via the following URL:

<http://ruritage.almende.com:3000>

2.1 Main screen

In the light version of the DSS, profile specification is done by means of filtering. As filters are applied, the list of matching Role Models becomes shorter. The replicator can then gain insight into the role model actions which could potentially lead to successful campaigns to reach their goals.

The current version of the DSS is pictured in Figure 2. It is composed of a title bar and two panels. The title bar contains the RURITAGE logo, the name of this tool and an About button that brings you to the official RURITAGE website. The left panel contains a number of filters which are applied to the results in the right panel. Both panels are described in more detail below.

Figure 2: DSS light version - main screen

2.2 Filters panel

The filters panel provides tools to help explore the data. By changing options in filters panel, the results panel is automatically updated. The results panel is explained later in this document. The filters panel contains one logic button and three groups of filters, each of which is explained below.

The Logic button (Figure 3) will combine the activated filters either with OR logic or AND Logic. These two types of logic work as follows:

- OR Logic - Displays Role Models that contain at least one of the activated filters
- AND Logic - Displays Role Models that contain all activated filters

To toggle the logic behavior between OR and AND, click on top of the logic button.

Figure 3: DSS light version - logic filter button

The filters are categorized by:

- SIAs - Systemic Innovation Areas
- Challenges - The challenges presented in Role Models
- Drivers - Factors which motivated a given project

Each filter category can be collapsed or expanded by clicking on top of it. By default they are expanded. An example category is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: DSS light version - SIA filter

Each category contains a Switch All button, a Search field and a list of options, each of which can be toggled between enabled and disabled state. By enabling or disabling the filters the user can combine different categories to extract useful information from the displayed Results. The Switch All toggle enables or disables all options within a category, and the Search field filters the items in a category by name while user is typing.

2.3 Results panel

The right panel contains the data of the Role Models which match the filters. The data of each resulting Role Model is contained in its own collapsible panel. Above the Role Model panels are some controls relevant to the format of the PROCESS data, which will be explained below.

By default each Role Model’s panel is collapsed, but it can be opened by clicking on the header (i.e. the green bar with the Role Model name). For example, the Role Model “rm10” is shown in Figure 5.

✓ rm10: Natural hazards as intangible CNH for human resilience in South Iceland (Iceland)

✓ PROCESS

N	L			C	E	N	N		C	C		C	C	H
1920	1930	1940	1950	1960	1970	1980	1990	2000	2010					

✓ ROLE MODEL ACTIONS

Relevance	Description
Very relevant	Discover and diffuse the traditional storytelling and superstitions as means to understand the natural environment and to promote the place ownership
Very relevant	Promote a participative process in order to create a cohesive resilient community (educational activities and event, monitoring and rescue teams, etc.)
Relevant	Promote the awareness of the natural features acting as hazard barriers
Relevant	Foster the knowledge and awareness of the link between the traditional construction techniques and the natural environment

✓ BARRIERS

Description

lack of coordination in rescue activities-overcome through new guidelines and planning procedures

lack of governmental institutions overseeing and managing cultural heritage

✓ CONTEXT

Description

GEOGRAPHY KATLA is a geopark in central-South-Iceland. and covers 9542 km2 or around 9,3 % of the total area of Iceland with population around 2700. Active volcanic area. Mountains, coastline, lakes, waterfalls, rivers, lava fields, caves, etc. A top priority of the park is to protect the natural environment, promote local sustainable development, introduce local culture and place a strong emphasis on nature tourism.

MAIN ECONOMIC SECTOR EDUCATION AND AGRICULTURE (sheep and dairy farming). Followed by construction, healthcare and commerce/vehicle repairation.

SIZE OF INFLUENCE

Figure 5: DSS light version - detailed Role Model data

Each Role Model panel contains several subpanels, each of which contain data about that Role Model. Each subpanel is collapsible, but the default state is open. The following subpanels are included in the current version of the DSS:

- **PROCESS:** A timeline of events which took place throughout the implementation of the heritage-led regeneration strategy of the Role Model at hand. When the mouse hovers over an event in the timeline then additional information is included about that event, including the year, conceptual step and milestone. The appearance of the timeline can be altered using the controls at the top of the results panel. The *Time* dropdown includes two options, where *View all time* changes the date range of the timeline to stretch across the earliest and latest dates present across all Role Models, and *Fit all graphs* fits the date range of each Role Model to include only dates relevant to that Role Model. When the *Stack* control is active, then the items in the timeline will be arranged such that events which overlap in time are stacked vertically.
- **ROLE MODEL ACTIONS:** A list of actions related to the Role Model (from the RURITAGE DoA), along with the relevance of the action.
- **BARRIERS:** A list of barriers to progress faced by the Role Model.
- **CONTEXT:** Information about the particular context of the Role Model, including geography, main economic sector and size of influence (size of the geographical area where the activities take place).

3. Future work on the DSS

Future work on the DSS will be directed by three different perspectives: user needs, technological innovation and integration with other tools. In the sections below, we highlight the most important ideas collected thus far, after which we present a roadmap with milestones for the period M13-M48 of the project.

3.1 User Needs perspective

First of all, the light version of the DSS, which is based on data from the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1) only, needs to be extended into a really useful version which includes the RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learnt (D1.2). This clear user need is in line with the main objective for the development of the DSS and needs immediate attention from M13 onwards.

Nevertheless, although the information considered in the DSS is in principle limited to the contents of the RURITAGE Practices Repository (D1.1) and the RURITAGE Inventory of Lessons Learnt (D1.2), there might be good opportunities to extend the information beyond these two deliverables, for example by including insights gained from further investigation into the “raw” data gathered during the summer and autumn campaigns (see below). Also, the users (Replicators) might be able to articulate their wishes regarding enhancements of the functionalities provided by the DSS. As the aim of partner ALM is to further exploit the DSS after completion of the RURITAGE project, it is of vital importance that we continuously have open ears for the feedback provided by end users.

During the RURITAGE Development Workshop in Heraklion, Crete, we have already found several directions for extending the DSS related to the user needs. The following aspects were mentioned as useful extensions by the various Replicators:

- The possibility to directly get in touch with experts in various crosscutting domains;
- Extension of the available data with complete stories with experiences of Role Models, in order to get a “feeling” about how things went during the implementation of the heritage-led regeneration strategies;
- Support for the creation of business models, and best practices related to business models;
- Ways to involve various stakeholders in the local area of the Replicator;
- Information about ideas for financing: plans, contact information and references to financing experts.

We will also further explore the “raw” data gathered in the project during the summer and autumn campaigns, potentially with the help of partner 3 (TECNALIA). Extensions and enhancements in this direction will be considered in the last phase of the project (after M28).

3.2 Technological Innovation perspective

Another important driver for the development of the DSS is to provide novel ways of support for Replicators (see the second objective related to the DSS development). In this sense, technological innovation is considered to play a key role in future development activities.

We have already investigated several new methods to inquire, process and present information to Replicators. Below, in Table 1, we show a few examples of visualisations of data that we will consider. Whether these can be realised, depends on the quality and quantity of the data available and the alignment with the other two perspectives regarding user needs and integration with other tools. Also, these visualisations require more sophisticated reasoning techniques to be implemented as software agents in the Processing Engine of the DSS. In particular, potentially with the help of partner 3 (TECNALIA), we hope to be able to find ways to **combine** good practices and Lessons Learnt from various RMs, thereby “allowing the choice of comprehensive programmes to be implemented at replicating sites”, as the DoA states. Furthermore, we aim at experimenting with using data about the interaction of the user with the system for implementing **learning mechanisms** into the DSS.

<p>Challenges Horizontal bar graphs can show the main challenges faced within group selection.</p>	
<p>Resources A radar graph or Kiviati diagram can indicate the most common available resources. It might aid the user to understand how similar regions are related to each other.</p>	
<p>Replicability A circular graph can show the replicability level of the selected RMs. By clicking on top of each level a popup window can also indicate which role models they belong to.</p>	
<p>Geographic Show Role Models geographic distribution. On click on top of each country it might bring the user to information about neighborhood information, average distance to close cities or any relevant places, and access quality (roads, public transport,...)</p>	
<p>Timelines Additional insights can be made about the timelines of each project and how they relate to each other</p>	
<p>Capital Transfer Mechanisms Frequency of categorical variables can be displayed</p>	
<p>Effort over time Show an effort graph of the selected Role Models, where the y-axis shows the number of activities being carried out at a given point in time. A similar graph can be used to indicate effort of newly formed strategies for Replicators.</p>	
<p>Expression frequency with sentiment analysis Bar graphs and word clouds can be used to indicate the frequency and tone of the most-used words in texts and stories the database.</p>	

Table 1: New visualisations considered during future development of the DSS

3.3 Integration with other Tools perspective

Given the fact that the DSS will eventually become part of the RURITAGE Replication Toolbox (D5.4), it seems logical to integrate the DSS with other tools in the Toolbox. In this direction, further integration with the RURITAGE Atlas beyond the shared database can be considered, but also integration with the RURITAGE Serious Game Kit (D2.2) and the Digital Rural Heritage Hub (RHH, developed in WP5). The possibilities will be investigated after M22, when the first version of most of the tools are expected to be ready.

3.4 Roadmap for further development of the DSS

The above considerations have led to a roadmap for future work on the DSS, as presented in Table 2. We indicate several additional milestones. After each milestones, RURITAGE and additional Replicators will be asked to test the DSS and provide feedback.

Completion Month	Milestone
End M16	Inclusion of Lessons Learnt. As needed for the main objective of the development of the DSS, it is crucial that we first focus on the inclusion of the Lessons Learnt. A first version of the DSS with Lessons Learnt will be ready before the Launch Workshops in M18.
End M22	Selection and Implementation of Technological Innovations. By M22, we will have investigated, prioritised and selected at least 5 technology enhancements to the Processing Engine of the DSS, based on the insights gained during the realisation of the main objective for the DSS and talks with technology and user partners. We have implemented at least 2 new functional enhancements to the DSS.
End M28	Integration with other tools. By M28, we will have investigated the integration with at least 1 other tool (like the Digital RHH), and have implemented a first version of this integration.
End M34	Re-investigation and Implementation of User Needs. By M34, we will have created an overview of additional (high-level) user needs that popped up during the period M18-M34. Combined with earlier insights, we have prioritised these user needs and realised a shortlist of at least 3 user needs with priority. We have implemented in the DSS the items contained in the shortlist.
End M40	Further Implementation. By M28, we will have implemented 3 more functional enhancements to the DSS based on the selection of technological innovations made earlier. We also have realised, if possible, further steps in the integration with other tools and the addressing of additional user needs beyond the shortlist mentioned earlier.
End M46	Roundup and Final Evaluation. A final version of the RURITAGE DSS will be made available to all users. Evaluation of DSS will be carried out by analysing the generation of customized solutions for the six Replicators considered in the project, and validating these against the insights gained through the monitoring phase.

Table 2: Roadmap for further development of the DSS (M13-M48)